

LOCAL PEOPLE'S PERCEPTION OF CERAMIC BEADS IN KUCHING, SARAWAK

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Abstract:

This study investigates the perception of ceramic beads among the local population, focusing on factors that increase young people's interest, affect the duration of the process, and analyze the community's perception of promoting beads using ceramic beads. The study, conducted in Kuching, reveals that the perception of residents towards ceramic beads is influenced by various factors. The findings highlight the importance of understanding community perception and offer recommendations for improvement.

Keywords: Ceramic Beads, Kuching, Community's Perceptions, Promotions

JEL classification: Z32

1. Introduction

Handicrafts in Sarawak, a diverse society with diverse ethnicities, are a valuable heritage that reflects the uniqueness of the products produced. The state's diverse handicrafts include forest products, soil, wood, and pandan, offering a variety of designs, motifs, patterns, and techniques used by entrepreneurs. This diverse culture and customs contribute to the richness of Sarawak's cultural heritage.

In addition, beads are also one of the handicraft products found in craft products. Beads have different types such as glass, agate, ceramic, and iron. Glass beads, or better-known Indo-Pacific beads are said to be the first produced in South India approximately 2400 years ago (Ramli, et. al, 2014). In Malaysia, ceramics is also known as clay that is molded and then fired at a certain temperature according to the type of clay (Savage & Norman, 1980). The compound or mixture that forms soil when mixed and dissolved with water is clay. Originally, ceramic beads were made by Orang Ulu and then the Iban people also started making ceramic beads from this clay. Among the popular products produced are bracelets, necklaces, earrings, and even anklets.

The researcher aims to understand residents' perceptions of ceramic beads in Kuching, Sarawak, to understand their acceptance in the fashion and daily affairs sectors. The product is popular as jewelry for women and is used in various events and daily affairs.

2. Perception

According to Edward de Bono (1969), thinking is a process that occurs in two phases, the first phase is perception, and the second phase is logic. Perception is an important element because it works in opening and preparing the thinking screen at an early stage. This process takes place continuously in individuals until they reach the end of life.

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2.1 Beads

Beads are one of the most popular handicraft products in Sarawak and the earliest beads found are in the Neolithic site of Gua Niah, Sarawak aged 2500 - 1000 BC (Zuliskandar et. al, 2013). Another word for beads used in Sarawak is 'marik' which comes from Sanskrit which means precious stone.

2.2 Ceramics

Ceramic refers to objects made of clay and fired at certain temperatures (Nurhadi et. al, 2008: 1). The word ceramic also comes from the Greek word, "keramos" which means clay (Asyaari, 2010: 4).

2.3 Theory of Perception

Diagram 1: Theory of Perception

Source: Theory of Perception (Joanes, Soffian, Goh & Kadir, 2014)

A term to describe the application of neurological research and accepted psychological principles in studying visual communication is perception theory. The perceptual theory deals with how the brain receives information, processes it, and uses it. In the theory of perception, the theorizing approach adds new information to study visual communication and helps people with the effectiveness of communication theory (Joanes, Ahmad Soffian, Goh & Kadir, 2014). The process of formation of perception begins with the reception of aspects of touch, sound, sight, taste, or aroma through the human senses and so on to form a sensation.

The process will also be selected and accepted when affected by the first process above. Factors such as individual expectations, motivation, and attitude undergo the screening process. By experiencing the process of perception, we will be more sensitive to the situation around us. There are several types of perception that can be classified into five parts, namely, auditory perception, visual perception, kinesthetics-tactile perception, social perception, and extra-sensory perception. The three main categories of perception are visual perception, auditory perception, and kinesthetic-tactile perception.

2.4 Visual Perception

The eyes are the most important element in creating perception because the eyes can detect and analyze colour, shape, size, pattern, position, and so on. Therefore, visual perception involves the sense of sight, which is the eye. In addition, the eye is a sense that can detect light stimulation and is the most important organ in the human body. Visual perception also means the ability to translate from the eye, which is the fall of light into the retina of the eye and is known as vision.

2.5 Kinesthetics – Tactile Perception

This perception involves three senses namely taste, smell, and touch, and is very important to balance auditory perception and visual perception. The sense of smell is capable of detecting stimuli

produced by pungent chemicals. The human nose has a pair of external openings with hairs capable of filtering dust. The sense of taste can detect the stimulation produced by flavoring chemicals. Known as the tongue, the muscular organ is in the oral cavity and is also one of the sensory organs that is sensitive to chemical stimuli and flavouring substances. Whereas, the sense of touch, it is a sense that is sensitive to the touch stimulation imposed by certain objects. Leather is the organ involved. The skin is divided into two layers known as the dermis (inner layer) and the epidermis (outer layer).

2.6 Extra Sensory Perception

This perception is a person's ability to perceive above his senses. First used by a parapsychologist from America in the 1930s, Sir Richard Burton 1870. Extrasensory perception is concluded as an ability that can be developed and applied to everyone.

Perception is also discussed at length in psychology. A general Internet search for the keyword "perception" directs the reader to many psychology and cognitive websites where awareness and understanding of sensory information are discussed. This website addresses the mechanisms of sight and hearing, touch, taste, and smell. All of these are stimuli delivered to individuals and interpreted in specific and personal ways (McDonald, 2011).

3. Research Methodology

The researcher will use both methods to obtain information in detail such as secondary data sources and primary data. The data source is a source that helps researchers to get information that is required to complete the results of the study.

This research used closed-form questionnaires in this investigation. A structured question is referred to as a closed questionnaire. To make the form easy to fill out, the reply just uses the available responses to the question. The questionnaire is divided into four carefully thought-out sections: Statistics are discussed in Section A. The study's goals are mentioned in Sections B, C, and D.

3.1 Promotion carried out through the mass media can increase the interest of young people

Graph 1: Total frequency of promotions carried out through mass media able to increase the interest of young people.

The graph shows the amount of frequency for promotions carried out through mass media capable of increasing the interest of young people. Based on the bar chart above, the majority of respondents agree with the promotion carried out through mass media by 55.5% followed by strongly agreeing by 39.8%. Next, as many as 4.4% of respondents are not sure whether promotions carried out through the mass media are able to increase the interest of young people and lastly, 0.3% of respondents disagree.

3.2 Young people are more interested in promotions that use social media extensively

Graph 2: Young people are more interested in promotions that use social media extensively.

The graph shows the total frequency of affordable prices being one of the factors that increase the interest of young people. Based on the bar chart above, most respondents agree with a total of 51.0% followed by strongly agreeing with 45.1%. Meanwhile, 3.6% were unsure of the statement and 0.3% disagreed.

3.3 Affordable prices are one of the factors that increase the interest of young people

Graph 3: Affordable prices are one of the factors that increase the interest of young people.

The graph shows the total frequency of affordable prices being one of the factors that increase the interest of young people. Based on the bar chart above, most respondents agree with a total of 51.0% followed by strongly agreeing with 45.1%. Meanwhile, 3.6% were unsure of the statement and 0.3% disagreed.

3.4 There is difficulty in obtaining suitable clay in the production of ceramic beads

Graph 4: Total percentage of difficulties in obtaining suitable clay in the production of ceramic beads.

The graph shows the total percentage of difficulties in obtaining suitable clay in the production of ceramic beads. Based on the bar chart above, the majority of respondents 286 people consisting of agree and strongly agree Likert scale. Next, the statement above also found that 88 people are not sure if there is difficulty in obtaining suitable clay to produce ceramic beads. Finally, as many as 10 people disagreed with the above statement.

3.5 Regular use of raw materials produces quality ceramic beads

Graph 5: Regular use of raw materials produces quality ceramic beads.

The graph shows the total percentage of raw material usage to produce quality ceramic beads. Based on the above data analysis, the majority of respondents agreed to record a total of 242 people followed by strongly agreeing which is 113 respondents. Meanwhile, 27 people said they were not sure about the above statement. Finally, as many as 2 people disagree with the regular use of raw materials to produce quality ceramic beads.

3.6 The efficiency of the workforce leads to an efficient production process

Graph 6: The efficiency of the workforce leads to an efficient production process

The graph shows the total percentage of workforce efficiency leading to an efficient production process. Based on the bar chart above, the majority of respondents agreed with the statement and recorded a total of 248 respondents followed by 118 who strongly agreed. Meanwhile, as many as 18 people are not sure about the above statement.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Cross-distribution analysis between genders with promotions carried out through the mass media can increase the interest of young people

Table 1: Crosstabulation genders * Promotions carried out through the mass media can increase the interest of young people.

		B1 Promotion carried out through the mass media can increase the interest of young people				
		Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Total
Gender	Male	54	74	9	0	137
	Female	99	139	8	1	247
Total		153	213	17	1	384

The table 1 above shows the cross distribution between genders with promotions carried out through the mass media able to increase the interest of young people in Kuching, Sarawak. Based on the cross distribution analysis above, the majority of local residents gave a positive response which was 95.3% while the majority of local residents who gave a negative response was 4.7%. Male respondents gave a positive response of 93.4% while male respondents gave a negative response of 6.6%. In addition, 96.4% of female respondents gave a positive response while 3.7% of female respondents gave a negative response. Female respondents were the most likely to agree that the promotion carried out through the mass media could increase the interest of young people in Kuching. In conclusion, local residents in Kuching agree with the use of mass media in promoting ceramic-based beads.

4.2 Age * Young people more interested in promotions that use social media extensively

Table 2: Age * Young people more interested in promotions that use social media extensively

		B2 Young people are more interested in promotions that use social media extensively			Total
		Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	
Umur	18-22 years old	34	53	1	88
	23-27 years old	38	76	1	115
	28-32 years old	15	19	1	35
	33-37 years old	8	9	0	17
	38-42 years old	11	13	0	24
	43-47 years old	14	15	0	29
	48-52 years old	18	11	2	31
	53-57 years old	13	7	1	21
	58 years old ke atas	16	8	0	24
Total		167	211	6	384

The table above shows that the majority of age groups gave a positive response of 98.4% while the majority of age groups gave a negative response of 1.6%. In addition, respondents who are in the age group of 23-27 years give a positive response of 99.1% while the majority of respondents who are in the age group of 48-52 years give a negative response of 6.5%. Therefore, ceramic bead craft entrepreneurs should diversify the use of social media platforms in increasing interest among young people. In conclusion, the majority of local residents in various age categories are interested in promotions that use social media extensively.

4.3 Employment status * affordability is one of the factors increasing the interest of young people

Table 3: Crosstabulation Employment Status * Affordability is one of the factors increasing the interest of young people

		B3 Affordable prices are one of the factors that increase the interest of young people				Total
		Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	
Job status	Government	49	52	2	1	104
	Private sector	21	14	1	0	36
	Unemployed	18	16	2	0	36
	Self-employed	13	11	1	0	25
	Student	72	103	8	0	183
Total		173	196	14	1	384

The table above shows a cross-distribution analysis between employment status and affordability as one of the factors increasing the interest of young people. Based on the analysis above, the majority of respondents according to employment status gave a positive response of 96% while the majority of respondents gave a negative response of 4%. In addition, the majority of local residents who work in the student sector gave a positive response of 96% while the majority of local residents gave a negative response of 4%. Therefore, affordable prices that can be owned by local people among students can be made to increase their interest in ceramic beads. In conclusion, the majority of local residents gave a

positive response and wanted an affordable price as one of the features that can attract the interest of young people.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the researcher has conducted a study on the Perception of Local Residents towards Ceramic Beads in Kuching, Sarawak. This study was conducted to identify the characteristics that can increase the interest of young people in ceramic beads, to study the factors that affect the duration of the ceramic bead-making process, and to analyse the community's perception of ceramic-based bead promotion methods.

Based on the research that has been done, the researcher can conclude that all three research objectives can be achieved through this study. This proves that the ceramic bead craft has various perceptions from the local population through factors that affect the duration of the manufacturing process and the promotional methods implemented in making this craft gain attention from the local population.

The researcher was also able to answer the questions that arose based on the research data which is the perception of the local population towards ceramic beads in Kuching, Sarawak is that in increasing the interest of the young people is the use of promotion through the mass media, using social media extensively, having a long durability, variety of functions and strategic store location.

able to further increase young people's interest in ceramic-based beads. In addition, the factors that affect the manufacturing process of ceramic beads are the sequence of raw materials used, the efficiency of the workforce, the selection of designs, the lack of skilled labour and the lack of research on the will of consumers. Meanwhile, effective promotion methods are the annual promotion of craft events, the use of social media platforms in displaying products, online purchases, buying products face-to-face, and direct interaction between sellers and buyers.

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